

FOREIGN EXCHANGE OPERATIONS OF COMMERCIAL BANKS AND THE NATURE OF THE EXCHANGE RATE, ITS TYPES AND FACTORS AFFECTING THE EXCHANGE RATE

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Abstract: In this article, the scientific-theoretical basis of providing modern and remote banking services in commercial banks and the economic importance of providing modern banking services in Uzbekistan are studied.

Keywords: banking services, remote banking services, modern banking services, internet banking, digital banking, online banking.

The word "Bank" is derived from the Italian word "Banca", which means "table", more precisely, "table with money". In the 12th century, the money changers in Genoa were called "Bancherii". If one of the moneylenders was untrustworthy and irresponsible in his work, he broke the table he was sitting on and was called "Banco rotto", that is, "bankrupt". The word "bankruptcy" known to us today is derived from the Italian word "Banca rotto".

A bank is an economic activity based on finance, which consists of attracting funds and carrying out funds and calculations. Economic perspective Banks act as intermediaries between those who have free cash in the money market and those who need additional resources.

First, it should be noted that the current banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan is fundamentally different from the banking system of the period before independence. It is known that at that time the core of the banking system was:

- USSR State Bank;
- Construction Bank;
- The state labor fund was established.

The main directions of the bank's work are the acceptance of deposits, the granting of loans and the provision of credit and account services to customers.

The bank also provides paid services such as safekeeping of securities, current management of securities transferred to safekeeping, execution of stock exchange orders, safe deposit box rental.

According to the implementation of various economic services, the following main types of banks are currently operating: central (issue) bank and commercial bank.

The Central Bank controls the country's total credit system, implements the state's monetary and credit policy, issues cash and securities, keeps the country's gold and currency reserves, and grants loans to state and commercial banks.

Commercial banks are divided into universal and specialized banks. A specialized bank consists of an investment bank, a savings (deposit) bank, a special bank, a cooperative bank, and others.

The commercial bank is a universal bank that provides a variety of banking services to individuals and legal entities (attracting deposits, promissory note accounts, lending, sale and purchase of securities). This bank is the core of the banking and credit system.

According to the form of ownership, there are the following types of banks: state bank, mixed bank with state participation, interstate bank, international bank, bank with foreign investment, joint-stock bank, banker's house, cooperative bank, local self-owned self-management bank, communal bank, private bank, etc. The strategy of formation and development of the banking system of the Republic of Uzbekistan corresponds to the program of gradual transition of economy to market conditions.

In the course of banking reforms in the past period, the 2-level structure of the national banking system (the Central Bank at the upper level, commercial banks at the lower level) was legally strengthened; the number of banks and the types of services they provide have increased.

The Central Bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which includes the Republic of Karakalpakstan, 12 regions and Tashkent city administrations, is the main bank of the Republic of Uzbekistan (the Uzbekistan branch of the former State Bank of the USSR until September 1992).

The lower stage of the banking system in the republic is made up of banks established on the basis of share ownership, as well as with the participation of foreign capital, their branches and representative offices, cooperative and private banks.

A bank is a commercial organization, a legal entity that performs the following types of activities, which are considered banking activities:

- ✓ accepting deposits from legal entities and individuals;
- ✓ risking loans from received funds;
- ✓ use for investment;
- ✓ making payments.

So, a bank is a large institution that embodies and accumulates funds, gives loans, keeps money accounts, issues money and securities, and performs transactions with gold and foreign currencies.

The World Bank improved the GDP growth forecast in Uzbekistan for 2022 to 5.3%. However, the growth in 2023 is estimated to be 4.9%. Also, through targeted social protection programs, the poverty rate is expected to decrease to 14.5% in 2023 and 12.2% in 2024.

Despite the consequences of the war in Ukraine, the economy of Uzbekistan is expected to grow by 5.3% in 2022. This is stated in the next report of the World Bank.

It is noted that fiscal policy is being continued in the country based on the need to soften the impact of this year's new shocks. If ongoing economic reforms continue to revive growth in the private sector, medium-term development may record positive indicators, the report said.

Uzbekistan has implemented a number of effective reforms on trade and price liberalization in recent years. However, additional reforms are needed to continue to stimulate productivity, private sector growth, and job creation.

The main focus should be on weak market factors, trade and transit costs, monopolies, regulatory environment and further strengthening of market stimulation and stability in agriculture and economy as a whole, experts of the World Bank note.

According to the data of the poverty line, in 2021, 17% of the population was included in this category. The increase in the amount and location of social assistance contributes to the decrease in the population of this stratum.

Depending on the uncertainty of the regional forecast, the GDP of 2022 microorganism increased by 5.4% at the expense of international remittances, exports and investments. In the second quarter, real wages increased by more than 6% compared to the same period last year. At the same time, growth in construction and agriculture partially offset the slowdown in growth in industry and services. Investments (mainly in energy production, fertilizers and infrastructure) increased by 9.4%.

The volume of exports increased by 40.5% compared to the same period last year, and gold exports more than doubled. The volume of exports of gold increased by 22.5%, and it corresponded to the contribution of natural gas, textiles, food, machinery, transport and tourism.

Imports increased by 7.4% as imported food and energy prices rose, as did domestic demand. Food exports increased by 41%, machinery and equipment by 29%, and imports by 65%.

In response to exchange rate pressures and an uncertain inflation forecast, the Central Bank initially raised the key rate to 17%. In June and July 2022, the stabilization of the exchange rate, the recovery of foreign exchange flows and the growth of domestic deposits allowed the Central Bank to reduce the policy rate to 15%.

Capital depletion following the war in Ukraine and more cautious bank policies slowed credit growth to 14% at the end of June 2022 from 23% in 2021.

In 2022, economic growth indicators in Uzbekistan are predicted to be 5.3 percent. Increasing logistical problems related to sanctions against Russia are expected to hinder the growth of private consumption. Private investments and exports can grow.

Also, the current account balance will improve, as Uzbekistan will benefit from the increase in raw material prices (gold, copper, natural gas) and the increase in remittances. The volume of direct investments is not expected to increase this year, the trade deficit will be financed mainly from the state budget.

Fiscal consolidation expected until 2023 is now expected to be delayed as targeted social protection increases in response to rising food prices and the impact of the war in Ukraine. Continued growth and expanded social protection programs are expected to drive poverty reduction, with the national poverty rate expected to fall to 14.5% in 2023 and 12.2% in 2024.

Nevertheless, it is predicted that in the coming years, the reciprocity of expenditures will be restored, supported by the redirection of revenues and the efficiency of expenditures. The government is expected to continue to adhere to the total debt limits, with public debt and total external debt gradually falling to 32 and 55% of GDP by the end of 2024.

Sources of financial resources of banks and their placement are reflected in the accounting balance sheet. The balance sheet of the bank is the mutual equality of the two sides consisting of the active and passive part. The liabilities of the bank's balance sheet reflect the sources of financial resources, and its assets reflect the placement of financial resources for appropriate purposes.

The liabilities of the bank balance include the following financial sources.

- Bank's own funds:
- authorized capital;

- emission income;
- reserve capital;
- retained earnings;
- net profit;
- subordinated debt obligations;
- other sources.
- Funds raised by the bank:
- deposits;
- open-ended deposits;
- savings certificates;
- term deposits;
- interbank loans;
- funds formed at the expense of the issue of securities;
- Credit from the Central Bank;
- Revenues and other liabilities.

Banks invest funds raised as a result of passive operations in active operations.

The assets of the bank's balance sheet consist of the following:

- Cash and equivalent monetary documents;
- Funds in the Central Bank and other banks;
- Loans;
- Investments;
- Deposited funds;
- rental and leasing;
- Fixed assets and other properties;
- Expenses;
- Other assets.

Bank operations are grouped as follows:

- ✓ cash operations (cash services);
- ✓ settlement operations (settlement services);
- ✓ credit operations (investment of funds);
- ✓ deposit operations (attraction of funds);
- ✓ operations with securities (sale and purchase);
- ✓ operations with foreign currencies;

- ✓ interbank operations;
- ✓ internal operations of the bank (movement of properties, capital and funds);
- ✓ other operations related to the result of activity.

The above-mentioned transactions are reflected in the double-sided accounting records, the main elements of which are: documentation; inventory; assessment; account number; double-sided writing; balance; financial statements.

Elements of accounting in banks are inextricably linked with accounting in other sectors of the economy. This relationship is also reflected in the balance sheets of enterprises and organizations of cash, settlement, credit and other operations carried out by the bank.

Summary A bank is a financial institution, the main activity of which is the attraction and placement of funds, in particular, the implementation of calculations. From an economic point of view, banks act as intermediaries between those who have free cash in the money market and those who need additional resources.

The main directions of the bank's work are the acceptance of deposits, the granting of loans and the provision of credit and account services to customers.

The bank also provides paid services such as safekeeping of securities, current management of securities transferred to safekeeping, execution of stock exchange orders, safe deposit box rental.

Uzbekistan has implemented a number of effective reforms on trade and price liberalization in recent years. However, additional reforms are needed to continue to stimulate productivity, private sector growth, and job creation.

The main focus should be on market weaknesses, trade and transit costs, monopolies, the regulatory environment, and strengthening stability to stimulate the market in agriculture and the economy as a whole, World Bank experts note.

Sources of financial resources of banks and their placement are reflected in the accounting balance sheet. The balance sheet of the bank is the mutual equality of the two sides consisting of the active and passive part. The liabilities of the bank's balance sheet reflect the sources of financial resources, while its assets reflect the placement of financial resources for appropriate purposes.

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